

Effect of Zn on the uptake of Cd by fenugreek (*Trigonella foenumgraecum* L.)

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Abstract : A pot experiment was arranged to study the effect of zinc on the uptake of cadmium by fenugreek. Cadmium was applied as CdCO_3 at the rate of 0, 5, 10 and 15 mg kg^{-1} and zinc was applied as ZnSO_4 at the rate of 0, 40, 60 and 80 mg kg^{-1} . It was observed that the yield of fenugreek was decreased with the single application of cadmium. But when it was applied with zinc, the yield was improved. The reduced uptake of Cd was observed in Zn treated pots. The response of Zn was observed ameliorative in Cd contaminated pots.

Keywords : Cadmium, zinc, fenugreek, uptake.

Introduction

The main goal of the subject is the understanding of behaviour of metals in the soil, their uptake by plants and the relationship with the environment. The anthropogenic use of heavy metals either through sewage-sludge or through fertilizers have received much attention due to enrichment of heavy metals in soil which impacts human health and social problems¹⁻³. Among toxic heavy metals, cadmium is of great environment concern because of its higher bioavailability in soil-plant relationship and toxicity to human and livestock by readily getting in to food chain⁴.

Sewage sludge is a product of waste water treatment processes which tends to concentrate potential contaminants such as pesticides, metals, pathogens, industrial solvents, dyes plasticizers and other organic chemical residues⁵.

Increasing industrial production, utilization of fertilizers or natural sources may elevate content of heavy metals in the environment. This can be potentially dangerous for human health due to their bio-toxicity and high bioaccumulation throughout the food chain⁶. The present paper reports the effect of zinc on the uptake of cadmium in fenugreek.

Results and discussion

The data presented in Table 1 (Fig. 1) indicated almost highly significant effects of Cd, Zn and Cd \times Zn interaction on influencing the dry matter yield of

Table 1. Effect of Cd \times Zn interaction on dry biomass yield of fenugreek (g/pots)

Cd-rate (mg kg^{-1})	Zn-source	Zn-rate (mg kg^{-1})	Yield (g/pot)
0	ZnSO_4	0	20.43 \pm 2.9
		40	20.94 \pm 2.7
		60	20.50 \pm 1.7
		80	20.41 \pm 1.9
5	ZnSO_4	0	21.00 \pm 2.6
		40	21.13 \pm 1.9
		60	20.97 \pm 3.5
		80	20.75 \pm 2.6
10	ZnSO_4	0	19.77 \pm 2.9
		40	20.63 \pm 1.3
		60	20.53 \pm 1.3
		80	20.51 \pm 1.8
15	ZnSO_4	0	19.42 \pm 1.5
		40	20.46 \pm 1.5
		60	20.41 \pm 1.5
		80	20.01 \pm 2.6
SE =			2.98
CD =			6.08

Sixteen treatments comprising I Control; II Zn 40 mg kg^{-1} (abbreviated as Zn 40, and the similar meaning was for the follows); III Zn 60; IV Zn 80; V Cd 5; VI Cd 5 + Zn 40; VII Cd 5 + 60; VIII Cd 5 + Zn 80; IX Cd 10; X Cd 10 + Zn 40; XI Cd 10 + Zn 60; XII Cd 10 + Zn 80; XIII Cd 15; XIV Cd 15 + Zn 40; XV Cd 15 + Zn 60; XVI Cd 15 + Zn 80, were replicated thrice (mean \pm SD) under Factorial R.B.D. Design at 5% level of significance.

Fig. 1. Effect of Cd × Zn interaction on dry biomass yield of fenugreek.

fenugreek, which decreased as the doses of Cd increased up to 15 ppm. However, application on Zn up to 40 mg kg⁻¹ either singly or in combination increased the dry matter content of all the pots, which resulted in 3.4% extra dry matter yield over the control. But its higher level (beyond 60 ppm) antagonistically influenced the dry matter yield of the fenugreek. The Cd × Zn interaction was observed non-significant. The pronounced and diminutive effect on dry matter yield was observed only in Cd added pots which recorded 4.9% less over the control. Therefore, the response of Zn was observed ameliorative and encouraging in Cd contaminated pots⁷. The adverse effect of Cd on the dry matter of fenugreek was observed higher in magnitude than that of Zn. The decrease in yield may be due to reduced photosynthetic rate and internal water deficit in shoot system due to poor root development.

The data presented in Table 2 (Figs. 2 and 3) indicated that the effect of Cd, Zn and Cd × Zn interaction were observed almost highly significant. Accumulation of Cd in root and shoot of fenugreek significantly increased as the doses of Cd increased up to 15 mg kg⁻¹. However, application of Zn antagonistically either singly or in combination reduced the Cd uptake in fenugreek. Application of Zn up to 80 mg kg⁻¹ resulted in retarded or almost negligible accumulation of Cd in plants. Application of recommended doses of Zn in crops would be beneficial for combating Cd-toxication of plant⁷. It appeared that application of Zn up to lower level (40 mg kg⁻¹) slightly increased the Cd uptake by shoots in some pots also. However, application of Zn antagonistically

Table 2. Effect of applied cadmium and zinc on Cd concentration (mg kg⁻¹) in fenugreek roots and shoots

Cd-rate	Zn-source (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn-rate (mg kg ⁻¹)	Cd concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)	
			Root	Shoot
0	ZnSO ₄	0	0.26 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.01
		40	0.16 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.05
		60	0.12 ± 0.01	0.21 ± 0.06
		80	0.10 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.02
5	ZnSO ₄	0	1.30 ± 0.18	0.91 ± 0.01
		40	0.73 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.01
		60	0.36 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.02
		80	0.26 ± 0.02	0.13 ± 0.02
10	ZnSO ₄	0	2.43 ± 0.02	1.33 ± 0.01
		40	1.30 ± 0.02	1.10 ± 0.10
		60	0.32 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.02
		80	0.24 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02
15	ZnSO ₄	0	2.85 ± 0.05	2.10 ± 0.17
		40	1.34 ± 0.04	1.10 ± 0.02
		60	0.63 ± 0.04	0.51 ± 0.67
		80	0.16 ± 0.03	0.13 ± 0.02
SE =			0.11	0.11
CD =			0.22	0.23

Foot Note are same as Table 1.

Fig. 2. Effect of Cd × Zn interaction on uptake of Cd in root of fenugreek.

either singly or in combination reduced the Cd uptake in crop. Thus Cd and Zn interaction exhibited an antagonistic effect on Cd concentration in roots of fenugreek plants⁸.

Cd and Zn have almost similar ionic radii, the simultaneous addition of both Cd and Zn reduced the adsorption of both ions. The interaction of Cd with Zn in plants is based on the substitution of Cd with Zn and decrease in Cd below its phytotoxic concentration in tissues^{9,10}.

Fig. 3. Effect of Cd \times Zn interaction on the uptake of Cd by shoot of fenugreek.

Material and methods :

Zinc sulphate was selected for the study of interaction between Cd \times Zn on fenugreek. For this purpose, a pot experiment was arranged. The soil used was alluvial, collected from Sheila Dhar Institute Experimental Farm (Texture : silty clay loam, clay : 362 g kg⁻¹, CEC : 20.6 Cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹, Organic C : 5.1 g kg⁻¹ and DTPA-Cd : 0.36 mg kg⁻¹), initial pH of the soil was 7.5 which increased to 7.7 after irrigation. Plastic pots of a 5 litre capacity (each containing 5 kg of soil) were used. After 24 h of the treatments, seeds were sown. Soil moisture was maintained by irrigating the crops at intervals of 5-6 days. Fenugreek was grown as test crop.

Zn was applied as ZnSO₄ to provide Zn at the rate of 0, 40, 60 and 80 mg kg⁻¹. Cd was applied as CdCO₃ at the rate of 0, 5, 10 and 15 mg kg⁻¹ of soil with three replications of each treatment. Soil in each pot was mixed thoroughly to ensure intimate distribution of applied Cd and Zn.

Silt and clay were separated by Pipette method and fine sand by decantation. Heavy metals were determined with Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectrometry (ICP-AES; Model-LABTEM, Perkin-Elmer, Inc.) at Central Environmental Pollution Control Lab, Indian Farmers Fertilizers Cooperative Ltd. (IFFCO), Phulpur¹¹. Diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid (DTPA) solution was prepared to extract the available heavy metals in soil samples¹². Soil pH was estimated in the 1 : 2.5 (soil : water) suspension using glass electrode pH meter. Organic carbon was determined by chromic acid digestion method¹³ and CEC by using neutral ammonium acetate solution¹⁴.

Heavy metals in plants were determined by tri-acid mixture (HNO₃, conc. H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ in 5 : 1 : 1 ratio)¹⁵.

Statistical analysis :

Data were analyzed by factorial analysis of variation (ANOVA) using various treatments as independent factors with the help of the sum of square (SS) and degree of freedom (DF). The standard error (SE) is given by $SE = \sqrt{2V_E/n}$ where, V_E is the variance due to the error, n is the number of replications, and the critical difference (CD) is given by $CD = SE_{diff.} \times t_{5\%}$ ($t_{5\%} = 2.042$ at $DF_{error} = 30$ was observed) and standard deviation (S_{yx}) were determined in accordance with¹⁶.

Conclusions :

The dry biomass yield of fenugreek was decreased (4.9%) with the single application (Cd 15 mg kg⁻¹) and increased (3.4%) with the combinatorial application (Cd 5 + Zn 40 mg kg⁻¹) compared to control.

The results indicate that the application of 15 mg kg⁻¹ soil enriched the content of Cd up to 10.9 folds in roots and up to 35 folds in shoots of fenugreek compared to control. When used combinatorial application (Cd 15 + Zn 80 mg kg⁻¹) soil decreased the content of cadmium up to 0.61 folds in root and up to 2.1 folds in shoots of fenugreek.

The reduced uptake of Cd was observed in zinc treated plots. An ameliorative effect of zinc was observed in Cd-contaminated soil. The results of presented study showed that zinc can effectively immobilize Cd in the soil. Zinc has potential to reduce Cd accumulation in both root and shoot of the fenugreek.

The application of Zn to the soil possibly reduces Cd in the edible parts of the plants and helps to reduce the risk to the health of people living in metal contaminated areas. A more detailed study is required to grow fenugreek or other vegetable crops in metals contaminated areas and evaluate their growth and distribution of heavy metals in different edible parts of plants.

In view of the uncertainties that remain about the behaviour and effects of Cd in the food chain, it is desirable to minimize its concentration in crops that are grown on sewage-irrigated soils.

As the uptake of Cd is reduced in presence of Zn, a clear antagonism takes place. The addition of Zn is bound to decrease the uptake of Cd by the fenugreek. Where there is an access of industrial effluent rich in Cd, such amendments can be of practical value.

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